

THE INFLUENCE OF CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT AND RISK PERCEPTION ON DESTINATION IMAGE AND TOURIST RETURN INTENTIONS

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to provide an overview of perceived travel risk, celebrity endorsement, destination image, attitude, and intention to return tourists to Bali. The population of this study are domestic tourists who have visited Bali. The sample size used was 170 tourists with a purposive sampling method. The analysis technique used is descriptive analysis. The results showed that the perceived travel risk of tourists visiting Bali is very low. This means that tourists feel the risk of traveling to Bali is very low, while celebrity endorsements and destination image get very good ratings. Likewise, the attitude of tourists visiting Bali is also in the very good category, and their intention to return to Bali is also in the very high category. Therefore, it is important for tourism business managers in Bali to pay attention to perceived travel risk, celebrity endorsements, and destination image in order to build a positive attitude and increase intention to return to Bali.

Keywords: perceived travel risk, celebrity endorsement, destination image, attitude, intention to return.

INTRODUCTION

Bali is a popular destination in the world. This is shown by the very strong Balinese brand, including that from the results of a survey of foreign tourists, they know and remember the Bali brand more than Indonesia. However, during the Covid19 pandemic period, all tourist destinations experienced problems, namely in the form of a decrease in the number of tourist visits, both foreign tourists and local tourists. During the Covid-19 pandemic, foreign tourists decreased drastically, so that Bali was only visited by local tourists, and even then, the numbers were very low. Over time, the condition of the Covid-19 pandemic has gradually improved because people have received vaccines. The declining number of tourists visits also shows that the intention to return to Bali is still relatively low. Research that examines the intention to visit Bali has been studied by previous researchers, including: Sukaatmadja et al. (2022), Wardana et al. (2020); and Devi and Yasa (2021). From the results of this study and also supported by information obtained from tourists who have visited Bali, which encourages them to have the intention to visit again, including: the perceived travel risk they feel, whether the risk of traveling to Bali is high or low. Likewise, there are other variables that encourage them to have the intention to visit again, namely information obtained from celebrities who visited Bali. If they get good information from celebrity endorsements, it makes their intention to visit Bali higher. Furthermore, no less important is the image of destinations in Bali. If the image of the Bali destination is very good, it will also increase the intention to visit again.

These three variables also have an influence on the attitude of tourists before having the intention to visit again. If the perceived travel risk is low, their attitude towards a destination will be better. In

addition, tourist attitudes towards a destination can also be built from celebrity endorsements and a good destination image.

Based on the background of the existing problems, the aim of this research is to provide an overview of perceived travel risk, celebrity endorsement, destination image, attitudes, and intentions to visit Bali and to formulate a strategy to increase tourists' intention to return to Bali.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Perceived Travel Risk

Perceived risk can be explained as a subjective evaluation of the risk of threatening situations based on their characteristics and severity (Khan et al., 2019). Perceived risk when traveling in general or with specific destinations is strongly associated with the intention to change one's travel plans, travel to certain destinations or avoid certain destinations (Neuburger & Egger, 2021). Perceived travel risk can affect the choice of tourist destinations, most tourists tend to choose low-risk destinations for holidays or the sense of security they feel when traveling domestically. Perceived travel risk can lead to a decrease in travel demand (Khan et al., 2019; Neuburger & Egger, 2021; Sánchez-Cañizares, 2021; Joo et al. 2021). Travel risks can also make tourists' attitudes toward a destination unfavorable (Bae & Chang, 2021; Sukaatmadja et al., 2022). This variable has four measurements according to Neuburger & Egger (2021): 1) Tourism is massively affected by the corona virus; 2) I am afraid that the virus will be brought by tourists to my surroundings; 3) Travel should be prohibited to avoid wider spread of the virus; and 4) Currently, it is best not to travel to areas with coronavirus cases.

Celebrity Endorsements

Celebrity endorsement is closely related to a combination of a company's brand or a person's brand. Celebrities are individuals who can be identified and recognized by a particular audience, and whose activities are more in the sense of having more ability or resources to influence than the average individual in the audience (Olmedo et al., 2020). The goal being done is that celebrity fans will become fans of the products endorsed too. The person selected to be associated with the brand must have some sort of product-relevant association. Much research on celebrity endorsement has been carried out to increase purchase intention for a product (Chan et al., 2018; Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2019), strengthen brand image (Chan et al., 2018; Malik et al., 2018), and foster a positive attitude (Vidyanata et al., 2018; Parwati et al., 2021; Darmawan and Iriani, 2021; Nurliasari et al., 2021). However, research on celebrity endorsement in relation to tourism is still rare. The promotion strategy of using celebrity endorsements was also carried out by the Indonesian government in an effort to restore tourism conditions when Covid-19 hit Indonesia. This variable has three measurements according to Wachyuni and Priyambodo (2020): 1) Credibility; 2) Attractiveness; 3) power; 4) Capabilities

Destination Image

In the tourism context, destination image is closely related to tourists' experiences at the destination and their perceptions of it. Destination image is defined as an individual's mental representation of knowledge (beliefs), feelings, and overall perception of a particular destination (Liu et al., 2018). When tourists feel a positive image of a destination, they may have a positive attitude towards a destination and intend to revisit that destination (Liu et al., 2018). Kim and Stepchenkova (2015) and Pereira et al. (2019) found a significant impact of destination image on tourist attitudes. In addition, many tourism

and marketing studies show that destination image influences not only tourists' subjective perceptions, but also on evaluations of subsequent trips, and on their future travel intentions (Chan et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2018; Ahmad et al., 2021).

This variable has three measurements modified from the research by Kamase et al. (2021): 1) Congenital destination image; 2) Affective destination image; 3) Unique destination image

Attitude towards the Destination

Attitude is a feeling created by learning and experience, to respond in a consistent way to something and this predisposition may be favorable or unfavorable. Attitude according to Vidyanata et al. (2018) is the tendency of individuals to act in the form of closed responses to certain stimuli or objects. In tourism, attitude is the predisposition or feelings of tourists towards a holiday destination and tourism services for that destination, which is based on perceptions of tourism products and the attributes of that destination (Bresciani et al., 2015; Sanchez-Cañizares & Castillo-Canalejo, 2015). Other researchers state that the attitude factor is one of the aspects that influence individual behavior (Darmawan and Iriani, 2021; Nurliasari et al., 2021; Sukaatmadja et al., 2022). This variable has four measurements quoted from the research of Pereira et al. (2019): 1) Very good choice of places to visit; 2) View as a precious place; 3) A very pleasant tourist destination; and 4) Like a place as a tourist destination

Return Visit Intention

The intention to return in this study based on the tourism context is the intention of tourists to return to visit a destination in order to realize sustainable tourism (Wardana et al., 2020). The research results of Yang et al. (2021) show that travel intention is an individual's tendency and likelihood to travel to a destination. Intention to revisit refers to the tendency of tourists to return to a particular destination in the future (Chen et al., 2021). The intention to return to a destination is an important process to be realized in tourist behavior, which is generated by many factors. To identify the factors that influence tourist intentions including destination image, promotion strategies, risks, and positive attitudes of users will increase tourist behavioral intentions. This variable has three measurements modified from the research of Liu et al. (2018): 1) Recommendations; 2) Revisit; 3) Intention to travel in the future

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is descriptive research. Meaning, this research provides an overview of respondents' perceptions of perceived travel risk, celebrity endorsement, destination image, attitudes, and intention to return. This research carried out on tourists who have already visited Bali. Prior to the research, the research instrument was tested on 30 respondents to determine its validity and reliability. The results of the validity and reliability tests show that the correlation values of all indicators are above 0.30; and the results of the reliability test showed that the Cronbach's Alpha value for all variables was above 0.6, as presented in Table I. Furthermore, data collection was continued by distributing questionnaires to 170 tourists who had visited Bali. A sample of 170 respondents was then analyzed using an analytical tool, namely: descriptive analysis.

Table I. Instrument Validity and Reliability Test Results

Variable	Items	Pearson Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha □
Perceived Travel Risk (X1)	X1		0.851
	X1.1	0.866	
	X1.2	0.868	
	X1.3	0.858	
	X1.4	0.779	

Celebrity Endorsement (X2)	X2		0.776
	X2.1	0.821	
	X2.2	0.851	
	X2.3	0.837	
	X2.4	0.553	
Destination Image (Y1)	Y1		0.616
	Y1.1	0.820	
	Y1.2	0.769	
	Y1.3	0.662	
Attitudes Towards the destination (Y2)	Y2		0.865
	Y2.1	0.957	
	Y2.2	0.952	
	Y2.3	0.564	
	Y2.4	0.869	
Intention to Visit Again (Y3)	Y3		0.780
	Y3.1	0.703	
	Y3.2	0.793	
	Y3.3	0.982	

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description of Respondent Characteristics

The characteristics of the respondents in this study were seen from gender, age, status, last education, occupation, and income. The composition of the characteristics of the research respondents is presented in Figure I.

Figure I. Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of respondents according to the sex of tourists can be seen in Figure 1. Approximately 52.35% of respondents were female and 47.65% of respondents were male. The age of the respondents was mostly dominated by respondents aged 21-30 years as much as 44.71%. Based on status, the respondents to this study were dominated by tourists with unmarried status of 98 people with a percentage of 57.65 percent and married status of 72 tourists. Based on their last education, the

respondents to this study were dominated by tourists with a recent undergraduate education of 93 people with a percentage of 54.71 percent.

Based on the type of work, respondents to this study were dominated by tourists with jobs as private employees with a total of 54 people with a percentage of 31.76 percent and based on their total income, respondents to this study were dominated by tourists with total income of IDR 7.5 million – IDR 15 million 80 people with a percentage of 47.06 percent and the least are respondents with an income of less than Rp. 2.5 million as many as 7 people with a percentage of 4.07 percent.

Results of Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

The frequency distribution is obtained from the score of the respondents' answers. The interpretation of item scores in the research variables can be seen in Table II below.

Table II. Measurement Criteria Description of Research Variables

No.	Measurement Scale	Interpretation Perceived Travel and Return Intention	Celebrity Risk interpretation, Visit image, and attitude	endorsement destination
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very low	Very bad	
2	> 1.80 – 2.60	Low	Bad	
3	> 2.60 – 3.40	High enough	Pretty good	
4	> 3.40 – 4.20	Tall	Well	
5	> 4.20 – 5.00	Very high	Very good	

Source: Ghozali (2016)

The description of the descriptive statistical analysis of each variable is as follows:

Perceived travel risk (X1)

The variable Perceived travel risk is one of the variables related to attitude and intention to return to Bali. The variable of this study measures the Perceived travel risk owned by tourists with a quantitative approach, which is based on respondents' responses to the indicators of Perceived travel risk owned by tourists who wish to return to Bali, namely indicators of the impact of tourism from risk, feeling afraid to travel, prohibiting activities travel, and a desire not to travel. Respondents' perceptions of the variable Perceived travel risk can be seen in Table III.

Table III. Results of Descriptive Analysis of Perceived Travel Risk Variables (X1)

Indicator	Answer Score	Means	Interpretation
		1	2
		3	4
		5	
Impact of risks from traveling (X1.1)	98	61	3
Feelings of fear of traveling (X1.2)	90	67	6
Prohibiting tourism activities (X1.3)	103	57	4
Desire not to travel (X1.4)	104	55	4
Perceived travel risk			

Perceived travel risk that is felt by tourists is indicated by indicators of the impact of tourism on risk (X1.1), feelings of fear to travel (X1.2), forbidding tourism activities (X1.3), and the desire not to travel (X1.4). Based on Table III it can be seen that of the 170 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of domestic tourists towards the Perceived travel risk variable indicator has an average score of 1.54 and it is stated that the Perceived travel risk for traveling to Bali is very low. This illustrates a condition where respondents understand Perceived travel risk shown by tourists, namely based on the impact of the risk of traveling, feelings of fear of traveling, prohibiting tourism activities, and the desire not to travel is very low.

Of the four indicators of perceived travel risk, it turns out that the indicator of feeling afraid of traveling shows the highest mean value, which is equal to 1.6 while the lowest is the desire indicator not to travel with a mean value of 1.50. This illustrates that according to tourists the desire not to travel still need to be reduced or removed.

Celebrity endorsements (X2)

Measurements of tourist celebrity endorsements consist of: credibility (X2.1), attractiveness (X2.2), and power (X2.3). Based on Table IV it can be seen that of the 170 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of domestic tourists towards the celebrity endorsement variable indicator is in the high category with an average score of 4.61. This illustrates a condition that respondents understand celebrity endorsements with indicators of credibility, attractiveness, and power, as well as capability.

Table IV. Results of Descriptive Analysis of Celebrity endorsement Variables (X2)

Indicator	Answer	Score					Means	Interpretation
		1	2	3	4	5		
Credibility (X2.1)	0	1	10	37	122	4.65	Very good	
Attractiveness (X2.2)	0	0	13	45	112	4.58	Very good	
Power (X2.3)	0	0	14	45	111	4.57	Very good	
Capabilities (X2.4)	0	0	12	34	124	4.66	Very good	
Celebrity endorsements						4.61	Very good	

Of the four types of celebrity endorsement indicators, it turns out that the indicator value (X2.4) shows the highest mean value, which is equal to 4.66 while the lowest is the power indicator, which is equal to 4.57. This illustrates that tourist with credibility, attractiveness, and power, as well as capability can increase the intention to return but for the power of celebrity endorsements needs to be increased.

Destination image (Y1)

The destination image variable is one of the variables related to attitude and intention to return to Bali. This research variable measures destination image owned by tourists who wish to return to Bali with a quantitative approach, which is based on respondents' responses to destination image indicators owned by tourists who wish to visit Bali, namely cognitive destination image indicators, affective destination image, and destination image. unique destination. Respondents' perceptions of the destination image variable can be seen in Table V.

Table V. Results of Descriptive Analysis of Destination Image Variables (Y1) Indicator

Answer Score	Means					Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5	
Cognitive destination image (Y1.1)	0	0	8	27	135	4.75 Very good
Affective destination image (Y1.2)	0	0	8	25	137	4.76 Very good
Unique destination image (Y1.3)	0	0	7	44	119	4.66 Very good
Destination image						4.72 Very good

Destination image perceived by tourists who want to visit again is indicated by indicators of cognitive destination image (Y1.1), affective destination image (Y1.2), and unique destination image (Y1.3). Based on Table V it can be seen that of the 170 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of tourists towards the destination image variable indicator is very good. This illustrates a condition that respondents understand the destination image shown by tourists as indicated by cognitive destination images, affective destination images, and unique destination images.

The average value of the destination image variable is 4.72 which is included in the very good category. This means that tourists assess the image of Bali as a very good destination. However, because this research was conducted in early June - early July 2022 where the COVID-19 cases in Indonesia were on the decline, this was one of the factors in the results of respondents' answers like this. Of the three destination image indicators, it turns out that the affective destination image indicator shows the highest mean value, which is equal to 4.76, which is included in the very good category. Affective destination image has the highest value. This means that tourists rate the image of the Bali destination as very good, while the lowest is as a unique destination image with a mean value of 4.66. This illustrates that according to tourists; Bali has decreased in their assessment as a unique destination.

Attitude (Y2)

The attitude variable in this study measures tourist attitudes with a quantitative approach, which is based on respondents' responses to attitude indicators, namely good choices (Y2.1); view as a precious place (Y2.2); pleasant tourist destination (Y2.3); and liked as a tourist spot (Y2.4). Respondents' perceptions of attitude variables can be seen in Table VI.

Table VI. Results of Attitude Variable Descriptive Analysis (Y2)

Indicator	Answer Score					Means	Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	$\frac{5}{122}$		
Good choice (Y2.1)	0	0	7	41		4.68	Very good
Valuation as a valuable place (Y2.2)	0	0	13	32	125	4.66	Very good
Delightful travel destination (Y2.3)	0	0	10	40	120	4.65	Very good
Liked as a tourist spot (Y2.4)	0	0	12	39	119	4.63	Very good
Attitude						4.65	Very good

The attitude of tourists shown by the indicator is a good choice (Y2.1), is a valuable place (Y2.2), is fun (Y2.3), is something they like (Y2.4). Based on Table 6 it can be seen that of the 170 respondents studied, it turns out that in general tourist perceptions of the attitude variable are included in the very good category with an average score of 4.65. This illustrates a condition that respondents have a very good attitude towards destinations in Bali.

Of the four existing attitude indicators, it turns out that the indicator is a good choice for traveling to Bali showing the highest mean value, which is equal to 4.68, while the lowest is liking traveling to Bali with a mean value of 4.63.

Intention to Visit Again (Y3)

Measurement of the intention to return to prospective tourists consists of: recommendations (Y3.1), intending to visit again (Y3.2), visiting in the future (Y3.3). Based on Table VII it can be seen that of the 170 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of tourists towards the variable indicator of intention to return is in the very high category with an average score of 4.68. This illustrates a condition where the respondent understands the intention to visit again indicated by the recommendation indicator, intends to visit again, and visits in the future.

Table VII. Results of Descriptive Analysis of Return Intention Variable (Y3) Indicator

Answer Score	Means	Interpretation						
		1	2	3	4	$\frac{5}{132}$		
Recommendation (Y3.1)		0	2	7	29		4.71	Very high
Willing to visit again (Y3.2)		0	1	9	35	125	4.67	Very tall
Intend to visit in the future (Y3.3)		0	2	10	33	125	4.65	Very high
Return Intention							4.68	Very high

Of the three types of indicators of intention to return, it turns out that the indicator value recommending other parties to visit Bali (Y3.1) shows the highest mean value, which is equal to 4.71, while the lowest is the indicator of visiting in the future (Y3. 3), which is equal to 4.65. This illustrates that tourists have a very high intention to return to Bali, while tourists' intention to travel to Bali in the future needs to be increased.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis, it can be concluded that the perceived travel risk of tourists visiting Bali is rated average in the very low rating range. For celebrity endorsement and destination image, they get ratings in the very good category. Likewise for the attitude of tourists about tourist destinations in Bali, they get very good ratings. Furthermore, the intention to return to Bali will receive an assessment in the very high category range. This means that tourists' intention to return to Bali is very high due to the very low perceived travel risk, celebrity endorsement and very good destination image, as well as a very good attitude. For this reason, in the future it is important for business people in the field of tourism in Bali to pay attention to the variables of perceived travel risk, celebrity endorsement, destination image to create an increasingly positive attitude and ultimately have an impact on the intention to return to Bali. In addition, for future research it is necessary to analyze using inferential analysis.

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